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**Economic advantages of using online platforms for booking and selling
makeup services**

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***Abstract.** Modern trends in digitalization encompass all sectors of the economy, shaping new models of business process organization and consumer interaction. In the service sector, particularly in the beauty industry, this phenomenon is of special relevance, as the competitiveness of professionals is increasingly determined not only by their skills but also by their ability to integrate digital tools into their practice. In this regard, special attention should be paid to the study of the economic advantages of using online platforms that combine the functions of promotion, communication, booking, and service sales. The purpose of this study is to substantiate the economic effects of using online platforms in the professional activities of makeup artists and to identify their impact on the efficiency of business organizations. To achieve this goal, methods of comparative analysis, economic generalization, and SWOT analysis were employed, enabling a systematic assessment of both the advantages and limitations of digital solutions in the service sector. The results confirmed that the use of online platforms reduces marketing and administrative costs, contributes to revenue growth through customer base*

expansion and the introduction of package offers, optimizes time resources by automating booking processes, and enables a new level of management through the availability of statistical and analytical tools. A comparison of traditional and digital models of makeup artists' work demonstrated a significant difference in costs, profitability, and productivity in favor of the digital approach. The SWOT analysis revealed strengths (greater accessibility and reputational capital), weaknesses (dependence on digital infrastructure), opportunities (development of new forms of cooperation and entry into related markets), and threats (increasing competition and cyber risks). The conclusions substantiate that online platforms are not only a tool for optimizing operational activities but also a strategic factor of economic resilience for small businesses in the beauty sector. Their use fosters the development of a new business model that integrates the creative and commercial aspects of the makeup artist's profession, enhances competitiveness, and opens up prospects for long-term growth.

Keywords: *service digitalization, competitiveness, business model, customer base, cost optimization, strategic development.*

Економічні переваги застосування онлайн платформ для бронювання та продажу послуг візажиста

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Анотація. *Сучасні тенденції цифровізації охоплюють усі сфери економіки, формуючи нові моделі організації бізнес-процесів і взаємодії зі споживачами. У сфері послуг, зокрема в індустрії краси, це явище набуває особливої актуальності, оскільки конкурентоспроможність майстрів дедалі частіше визначається не лише професійними навичками, а й здатністю інтегрувати*

цифрові інструменти у власну діяльність. З огляду на це особливої уваги заслуговує дослідження економічних переваг застосування онлайн-платформ, які поєднують функції просування, комунікації, бронювання та продажу послуг. Метою дослідження є обґрунтування економічних ефектів використання онлайн-платформ у професійній діяльності візажистів та виявлення їхнього впливу на ефективність організації бізнесу. Для досягнення поставленої мети застосовано методи порівняльного аналізу, економічного узагальнення та SWOT-аналіз, що дозволило системно оцінити як переваги, так і обмеження цифрових рішень у сфері послуг. Отримані результати підтвердили, що використання онлайн-платформ знижує маркетингові та адміністративні витрати, сприяє зростанню доходів за рахунок розширення клієнтської бази й упровадження пакетних пропозицій, оптимізує часові ресурси шляхом автоматизації бронювання та формує нову якість управління завдяки наявності статистичних і аналітичних інструментів. Порівняння традиційної та цифрової моделей роботи візажиста продемонструвало суттєву різницю у витратах, дохідності та продуктивності на користь цифрового підходу. SWOT-аналіз дозволив виявити сильні сторони (зростання доступності та репутаційного капіталу), слабкі сторони (залежність від цифрової інфраструктури), можливості (розвиток нових форм співпраці, вихід на суміжні ринки) та загрози (посилення конкуренції, кіберризик). Тож онлайн-платформи є не лише інструментом оптимізації операційної діяльності, а й стратегічним фактором економічної стійкості малого бізнесу у сфері краси. Їхнє застосування сприяє формуванню нової бізнес-моделі, яка поєднує творчий і комерційний аспекти професії візажиста, підвищуючи конкурентоспроможність та відкриваючи перспективи для довгострокового розвитку.

Ключові слова: цифровізація послуг, конкурентоспроможність, бізнес-модель, клієнтська база, оптимізація витрат, стратегічний розвиток.

Problem statement. The modern development of the service sector is characterized by the intensive introduction of digital technologies, which not only change the content and forms of service provision but also alter the mechanisms of competition in the market. In these conditions, not only the quality and professionalism of performers, but also the speed, convenience and transparency of receiving services are of crucial importance. In the beauty industry, particularly among makeup artists, online platforms are becoming a key tool for adapting to new market challenges, combining functions such as promotion, communication, booking, and sales. Their use enables the reduction of costs, increases labor efficiency, and ensures stable income growth, thereby determining the strategic importance of digital solutions for the economic sustainability of small businesses in the beauty sector. At the same time, the introduction of digital technologies is multifaceted. On the one hand, the use of VR, e-commerce platforms and artificial intelligence algorithms ensures the renewal of business models, optimization of supply chains and an increase in the level of customer experience. [1, p. 106]. On the other hand, the integration of beauty tech solutions that combine personalization, informativeness and high quality of service creates new utilitarian and emotional values for consumers that directly affect their satisfaction and loyalty [2].

In addition, changes in consumer behavior that have intensified in the post-pandemic period confirm the growing importance of information platforms focused on the fashion context, aesthetics, and opportunities for self-expression, as these factors shape users' motivation to participate in digital service spaces actively. [3]. At the same time, it is worth noting that the demand for beauty services is formed not only under the influence of price or rating indicators, but also through indirect signals such as the number of free slots in the online booking system, which determines customer trust and perception of quality [4, p. 188].

Thus, the relevance of studying the use of technological innovations in the beauty industry lies in the fact that digital platforms are not only a technical means

of organizing processes, but also a significant behavioral, strategic, and marketing factor in shaping business competitiveness.

Analysis of recent research and publications. Current research in the field of online and electronic service booking systems indicates a growing interest among scholars in studying the impact of digital platforms on consumer behavior, management efficiency, and economic outcomes of service providers. Y. Cai et al. showed that proper planning and integration of electronic visits into the service schedule reduces negative consequences in the form of increased waiting times, uneven workload distribution between performers, and staff overload, and also increases operational efficiency [5]. Complementing these results, P. Zhao et al. summarized the experience of implementing web-based medical record systems that reduce the number of absences, shorten waiting times, and increase patient satisfaction. However, implementation is constrained by financial and technological barriers [6]. The scientific contribution of F. Kitsios et al. is to identify the dependence of patient satisfaction on the quality of the website and the functional characteristics of electronic record systems [7]. In a similar vein, F. Ostadmohammad and colleagues have highlighted that planning and management deficiencies at different levels of the system can create organizational difficulties and reduce user satisfaction [8]. The development of a web-based management system for beauty salons, presented by E. Blancaflor et al., proves that digitalization creates new opportunities for marketing and increasing the competitiveness of the industry in the post-pandemic period [9]. The practical aspect of the quality of digital services is emphasized by J. Moon and E. Yang, who proved that the quality of online reservation systems in beauty salons directly affects customer satisfaction and their intention to continue using them [10]. A. Ahmadi-Javid and co-authors have systematized optimization studies of outpatient appointment systems, highlighting strategic, tactical and operational decision levels and outlining directions for further research [11]. J. Perret and J. Schwientek investigated the impact of beauty tech, in

particular AR and AI solutions, on the formation of consumer experience, customer satisfaction and their loyalty, while proving that informativeness, personalization and quality of service determine the utilitarian and hedonistic aspects of interaction [2]. At the same time, V. Nazarenko demonstrated that makeup in modern mass media has evolved into a communicative code that reflects cultural norms, individuality, and social status, showcasing the combination of aesthetic and digital practices in the formation of visual identity [12]. The analysis is completed by the work of Y. Goh and colleagues, which proves that strategic «downtime» in recording systems with sequential servers can optimize schedules, balance customer waiting times and reduce total costs [13]. Thus, the literature review shows that online platforms and electronic booking systems, regardless of their scope, combine economic, organizational, and behavioral effects: they optimize the resources of service providers, increase management efficiency, while forming a new quality of interaction with consumers and opening up prospects for further scientific and applied research.

Highlighting previously unresolved parts of the general problem. Despite significant scientific interest in the issues of online platforms and electronic booking systems, several issues remain unresolved. In particular, most studies focus on the field of healthcare and tourism services, while the beauty industry, and especially the activities of makeup artists, remain understudied. In addition, scientists often ignore the issues of comparing economic effects for the two parties - the service provider and the consumer, as well as the strategic aspects of combining the creative and economic components in the beauty industry business model. Our study aims to fill this gap by comprehensively analyzing the economic benefits of using online platforms in the activities of makeup artists, revealing their impact on the organization of business processes and interaction with consumers, as well as identifying a two-way effect for performers and clients. The practical significance of the results lies in the possibility of their application to improve the work of beauty

specialists, increase the competitiveness of small businesses in the beauty industry and develop recommendations for integrating online tools into business processes.

Formulation of the objectives of the article (task statement). The purpose of the study is to identify and substantiate the economic benefits of using online platforms for booking and selling makeup artist services, in particular their impact on reducing costs, increasing income, optimizing time resources and forming an analytical base for the strategic development of business activities.

Presentation of the main material of the study. The current stage of economic development is characterized by intensive digitalization, which encompasses nearly all spheres of social life, from industry and education to culture and household services. In these conditions, digital tools become not only auxiliary elements of business but also a key factor in its competitiveness, transforming how interaction occurs between suppliers and consumers. Online platforms are the central element of this transformation, as they combine the functions of marketing, communication, booking and sales, forming a new architecture of the services market.

Their essence lies in creating an integrated digital environment where supply and demand meet, transaction costs are minimized, resource utilization is optimized, and process transparency is enhanced. At the same time, platforms also perform a behavioral function: thanks to visualization, personalization, and interactivity tools, they can create additional value for customers, influencing both the utilitarian and emotional aspects of the consumer experience [2]. The experience of leading beauty companies proves that the implementation of VR, e-commerce solutions, and artificial intelligence contributes to sales growth, increased customer satisfaction, and management efficiency [1, p. 110].

It is also essential that platforms in the service sector reflect a new logic of competition: for performers, they open up access to a broader customer base, but at the same time create risks of dependence on the policies of digital infrastructure

owners and increase the requirements for business model flexibility [14, p. 1858]. In the beauty industry, this means that masters must not only possess a high level of professional skills, but also be able to adapt to digital trends, utilize marketplaces, their own websites, or social networks with a booking function as channels for attracting customers. Varieties of such platforms can be conditionally divided into several groups (table 1), depending on their functionality and the level of control the entrepreneur has over the booking process and service promotion.

Table 1

Various types of online platforms for booking and selling services in the beauty sector

Platform type	Essence and characteristics	Examples for a makeup artist	Economic effect
Marketplaces	Aggregate a large number of offers, provide search and comparison of services, and standardize the booking process	Glovo Beauty, Treatwell, Booking-like services	Expanding the customer base, reducing advertising costs through centralized promotion
Specialized online booking programs	Software solutions for beauty salons and individual masters; combine booking, client management, scheduling, payments, and basic analytics	EasyWeek (free for individual masters, integration with Monobank, Stripe), BeautyPro (UAH 360–3600 /month), CleverBox: CRM (from UAH 700 /month), Appointer.ua (UAH 1599–6399 depending on the package), Acuity (UAH 350–600 /month)	Reduction of administrative costs, process automation, transparent analytics, and time optimization
Own websites and mobile applications	Give complete control over business processes: schedule, prices, communication with clients; form a unique brand and increase loyalty	Own business card website with integrated booking widget, makeup artist mobile application	Revenue growth through direct sales, increased margin and brand awareness

Platform type	Essence and characteristics	Examples for a makeup artist	Economic effect
Social networks with a booking function	Integrate booking into a visual promotion environment; combine content, advertising and booking in a single communication channel	Instagram (Shop + «Booking» button), Facebook Booking, TikTok for Business, Telegram bots with integration	Image formation, attracting a young audience, increasing trust through reviews, and rapid scaling of advertising campaigns

Source: author's development based on [4; 10; 15; 16; 17; 18; 19]

A comparison of online platforms reveals that their functionality and economic effects vary significantly depending on the organizational model. Marketplaces offer rapid scaling of the customer base through centralized promotion, but they also create the risk of high competition within the platform and dependence on its rules. Specialized online booking programs serve as a universal tool for small businesses, combining booking, CRM, and financial analytics, which helps reduce administrative costs and increase operational efficiency. Own websites and mobile applications allow you to form a unique business model and brand, but require additional costs for support and promotion. Social networks with integrated booking functions create the most dynamic channel for attracting customers, but their effectiveness largely depends on the activity and creativity of the performers themselves.

Thus, the choice of platform is determined by the strategic priorities of the master: market expansion, resource optimization or building a personalized brand. The most effective solution, in practical terms, is a combination of several solutions that allows you to leverage the advantages of different channels and minimize their limitations.

In the beauty industry, particularly among makeup artists, the role of such platforms is significant, as dynamic fashion trends, personalized customer expectations, and intense competition among masters shape demand.

In this case, the online space performs a dual function: it is simultaneously a virtual «showcase» of professional skills and work results and a tool for prompt

booking and sale of services. Demonstrating a portfolio in the format of photo and video content, the possibility of direct communication with consumers, integration of reviews and ratings, the use of calendars to optimize workload and synchronization with online payment create a new business model that combines the creative and commercial aspects of a makeup artist's activity. It is this adaptation to digital solutions that determines the competitiveness of a master in the services market, contributes to the formation of long-term relationships with clients and ensures the economic sustainability of his professional activities.

An essential component of this process is the economic benefits that directly shape the effectiveness of the makeup artist's business. First of all, digital platforms allow you to reduce costs significantly: automation of communications and client registration reduces the need for administrative resources, and built-in promotion mechanisms replace traditional advertising, reducing marketing costs.

Along with this, there is a noticeable increase in income, as platforms open up access to a broader client base, allowing you to form service packages, apply dynamic pricing and increase the average check.

A significant effect is also the optimization of time: automatic booking and synchronization with calendars ensure rational use of the working day and reduce the number of «empty slots» in the schedule. No less important is the transparency of activities, which is based on order statistics, ratings, and reviews, building customer trust and contributing to the increasing reputational value of the master.

The economic benefits of using online platforms in the activities of a makeup artist are manifested in many ways. For example, they include both an increase in financial results due to the expansion of the client base and diversification of income, and the optimization of work organization through the automation of routine processes. At the same time, digital solutions contribute to strengthening market positions and building the long-term competitiveness of small businesses (table 2).

Table 2

Economic effects of using online platforms in the activities of a makeup artist

Direction of influence	Traditional model	Online platforms	Economic effect
Marketing costs	High costs for print advertising, outdoor media, targeted advertising without precise coverage	Built-in promotion tools, organic traffic, reviews and ratings	Reduction of costs by 20-40%, increased efficiency of customer acquisition
Administrative costs	Payment of assistants or spending of the master's time on keeping records and reminders	Automated booking, calendars, synchronization with messages	Reduction of organizational costs, freeing up 5-7 hours of working time per week
Revenue from basic services	Limited client base, uneven loading	Expanded access to new clients, service packages, and dynamic pricing	Increase in the average check by 15-25%, stabilization of income
Revenue from related services	Minimal opportunity to offer additional products or consultations	Cross-selling (care products, online consultations), integration with e-commerce	Additional revenue growth of 10-15%
Time resources	High probability of empty slots in the schedule, lack of precise planning	Calendar synchronization, dynamic slot management, convenience for customers	Increase in the number of orders by 10-15%
Analytics and management	Lack of systematic data on customers and demand	Booking analytics, service popularity rating, and financial reports	Improvement of forecasting and strategic planning, increased competitiveness

Source: author's development

The presented data confirm that the use of online platforms transforms the economic side of the makeup artist's work comprehensively: it reduces marketing and administrative costs, ensures an increase in income from basic and related services, optimizes time resources and provides a new level of analytical support for

business management. At the same time, the benefits also extend to clients, who receive convenience in accessing services, the ability to quickly choose a time and transparency of calculations. Such mutual benefit makes digital tools not only an operational solution, but also a factor of strategic competitiveness. For a more in-depth assessment, it is advisable to compare the traditional and digital models of organizing work in the makeup field (table 3).

Table 3

Comparison of traditional and online models in the activities of a makeup artist

Criteria	Classic model (for makeup artists)	Online platform (for makeup artists)	Effect for the client
Costs	Significant advertising costs, the need to spend time on communication and organizational resources	Reduction in marketing and administrative costs due to automation and promotion with built-in tools	Access to complete information without additional calls or clarifications, saving time
Profitability	Limited customer base, uneven loading, and low opportunities for cross-selling	Wide access to new customers, formation of service packages, the possibility of online payment and cross-selling	Flexible choice among offers, discounts and packages, convenient payment terms
Efficiency	High probability of empty slots in the schedule, complexity of planning, and lack of analytics	Calendar synchronization, automatic booking, access to statistics and reviews	Quick registration at a convenient time, transparency of quality through rating and reviews
Trust and transparency	The consumer is guided only by personal recommendations and limited information	Public reviews, ratings, and examples of work are available in open access	Increased confidence in the choice, reducing the risk of non-compliance with expectations

Source: author’s development

Thus, online platforms not only allow for optimizing the cost structure by reducing marketing and administrative expenses, but also ensure stable revenue growth by expanding the client base and introducing innovative forms of customer

interaction. They contribute to uniform loading, reduce the risk of gaps in the work schedule and create conditions for increasing labor productivity. At the same time, it is essential to consider the two-way effect: for clients, digital solutions provide quick and convenient access to services, transparency of conditions, and increased trust in the master.

At the same time, a new quality of business management is emerging: order analytics, systematization of reviews, and integrated financial monitoring tools create an information basis for making strategic decisions. As a result, online platforms become not just an intermediary between the performer and the client, but a systemic tool for developing entrepreneurial activity, combining the creative and economic dimensions of the profession.

However, it is worth considering that the effects of the use of innovations are not always unambiguously positive. On the one hand, digital markets open up new sales channels; on the other hand, they increase the dependence of businesses on the policies of platform owners, which creates strategic risks [14, p. 1860]. In addition, when assessing the attractiveness of services, customers focus not only on the rating or price, but also on indirect signals, in particular the number of available booking slots, which can both increase interest and repel in conditions of lack of choice [4, p. 200]. Thus, the economic effectiveness of digital solutions is shaped by the complex interaction between the executive's management strategies and the behavioral reactions of consumers. At the same time, a comprehensive assessment of online platforms requires taking into account not only obvious advantages but also potential limitations, such as dependence on technological infrastructure, cybersecurity threats, additional commission costs, or increased competition in the digital environment. That is why it is advisable to use SWOT analysis, which allows you to systematically identify the strengths and weaknesses of using online platforms, as well as identify promising opportunities and risks for the makeup artist's business (table 4).

Table 4

SWOT analysis of the use of online platforms in the activities of a makeup artist

Strengths	Weaknesses
Cost reduction, expansion of the client base, process automation, and reputational capital through reviews	Dependence on Internet access, platform commissions, and the need for digital literacy
Opportunities	Threats
Development of new services (online consultations, e-commerce), entry into new market segments, partnership with brands	Increasing competition in the digital environment, cybersecurity risks, and changes in platform rules

Source: author's development

The results of the SWOT analysis confirm that the use of online platforms in the activities of a makeup artist is complex, combining obvious advantages with certain limitations and risks. Among the strengths, it is worth highlighting cost reduction, process automation, expanding the client base and building reputation capital through reviews and ratings. These factors form the basis for stability and long-term development. At the same time, weaknesses are related to dependence on digital infrastructure, the presence of platform commission payments and the need to constantly improve digital literacy.

At the same time, the digital environment opens up new opportunities, including the development of additional areas of activity (online consultations, partnerships with cosmetic brands, e-commerce integration), as well as access to new market segments. However, potential threats should not be ignored, including increased competition in the digital space, increased cybersecurity risks and possible regulatory changes in the field of platform activity. In the complex, such an assessment allows us to conclude that the effectiveness of using online platforms depends on a makeup artist's ability to combine their own strengths with external opportunities, minimizing risks and compensating for existing weaknesses, which creates a strategic space for sustainable business development in the digital economy.

Conclusions. The study revealed that digitalization is gradually encompassing all areas of economic activity, and online platforms are becoming a pivotal tool in transforming business models in the service sector. For makeup artists, they perform a dual function: on the one hand, they form a virtual showcase of professional skills and a means of brand promotion, and on the other hand, they provide automation of bookings, time optimization and improved quality of communication with clients. The economic benefits of using such platforms are manifested in several directions. First, they allow you to reduce marketing and administrative costs thanks to built-in tools for promotion and automation of organizational processes. Secondly, they create conditions for revenue growth through expanding the client base, introducing package offers and using dynamic pricing. Thirdly, they contribute to the rationalization of time use and stabilization of workload. Finally, the analytical functions of the platforms ensure transparency of activity results and form the basis for strategic planning. A comparative analysis of traditional and digital work models confirmed significant differences in favor of the online format, which combines financial benefits with efficient use of resources. SWOT analysis, in turn, allowed us to identify not only strengths and opportunities, but also to outline weaknesses and risks associated with digital dependence and the competitive environment.

Therefore, the use of online platforms is not only a tactical solution for optimizing a makeup artist's activities but also a strategic step that ensures economic sustainability, opens up new development opportunities, and strengthens competitive positions in the market. Further research can focus on quantifying the economic impact and analyzing the long-term effects of digital platforms on the profitability of small businesses in the beauty sector.

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